

Original Research

Impact of Digital Adoption and Digital Financial Literacy on MSME Growth with Financial Inclusion as a Mediating Variable

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of digital adoption and digital financial literacy on the growth of MSMEs by including financial inclusion as a mediating variable in MSMEs in NTB Province. Data were collected through a questionnaire survey and processed using the Structural Equation Modeling–Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) approach, with the evaluation stages of the measurement model (convergent validity and internal reliability) and structural model (hypothesis test and R-Square value). The results of the analysis showed that the entire construct met the criteria of validity and reliability, while the R-Square value for financial inclusion and MSME growth was above 0.70, indicating a strong model explainability. Substantively, digital adoption and digital financial literacy have a positive and significant effect on financial inclusion, and financial inclusion has a positive and significant effect on the growth of MSMEs. However, the direct influence of digital adoption and digital financial literacy on the growth of MSMEs is positive but not significant. In contrast, financial inclusion has been shown to significantly mediate the relationship between digital adoption and MSME growth, as well as between digital financial literacy and MSME growth. These findings conclude that digital transformation and the increase in financial literacy only have a real impact on the growth of MSMEs when followed by the active use of formal financial services, so the implication is that policies to strengthen MSMEs need to simultaneously encourage digitalization, financial education, and the expansion of financial inclusion.

Keywords: Digital Adoption, Digital Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, MSME Growth.

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Introduction

MSMEs constitute a fundamental component of Indonesia's economy (Putri & Husna, 2024; Susan, 2020). In 2021, they contributed 61.1% to national GDP and employed 97% of the workforce, totaling 117 million people (Kemenkeu RI, 2024). MSMEs comprise 66 million business units, representing 99% of all businesses (Kemenkeu RI, 2024). The sector's 2.24% contraction in 2020 during the Covid-19 pandemic revealed their vulnerability to external shocks (Putritamara et al., 2023; Saturwa et al., 2021; Tambunan, 2021). This downturn exposed deficiencies in resilience, financial accessibility, and business capacity (Bartik et al., 2020; Hanggraeni et al., 2019).

The West Nusa Tenggara (NTB) Province mirrors national trends while facing regional challenges (Gupta & Kumar Singh, 2023; Hanggraeni et al., 2019; Putri & Husna, 2024b). MSMEs in NTB increased from 100,000 units in 2019 to 120,000 units in 2023 (Dinas Koperasi Usaha Kecil dan Menengah, 2024), indicating effective local development strategies (Dwyanti, 2024; Kaharuddin et al., 2024; Prabowo et al., 2024). However, 84.16% are micro enterprises, 14.6% small, and 1.2% medium (Dinas Koperasi Usaha Kecil dan Menengah, 2024), showing limited competitiveness (Lakuma et al., 2019; Nursini, 2020; Rajamani et al., 2022).

Access to formal financial services remains constrained, with 80.9% of micro enterprises unbanked (Adelaja et al., 2024; Yang & Zhang, 2020). In NTB, MSME stakeholders have not recognized digital technology's strategic importance, affecting their financial management (Candraningrat et al., 2021; Dwyanti, 2024; Putri & Husna, 2024a). While FinTech has transformed financial transactions (Bushra & Mir, 2024; Hamid et al., 2024; Morgan, 2021), low digital adoption and literacy risk marginalizing MSMEs (Coco et al., 2024; Meldona et al., 2023; Sun & Zhang, 2024).

Digital financial literacy encompasses financial principles and secure use of digital tools like mobile banking, e-wallets, and digital lending services (Bire et al., 2019; Chibesa & Mwangi, 2025; Dwyanti, 2024; Sun & Zhang, 2024). Financial inclusion helps MSMEs expand market reach and improve efficiency (Omokhoa et al., 2024; Raj et al., 2024; Sun & Zhang, 2024; Sutrisno et al., 2024), while insufficient inclusion may limit digitalization benefits (Becha et al., 2025; Dwyanti, 2024; Prabowo et al., 2024; Sun & Zhang, 2024).

Despite extensive research, the effects of digital adoption, financial literacy, and inclusion on MSME growth remain unclear (Adhikari et al., 2024; Becha et al., 2025; Usmaniyah & Abrori, 2024). The literature shows divergent findings on financial access, literacy, and MSME performance (Charfeddine et al., 2024; Dwyanti, 2024; Gunawan et al., 2023; Hamid et al., 2024; Rajamani et al., 2022; Usmaniyah & Abrori, 2024). Some studies suggest FinTech innovations enhance inclusion, while others argue they may worsen exclusion for low literacy users (Ebirim & Odonkor, 2024; Elouaourti & Ibourk, 2024; Gopalan & Rajan, 2022; Odei-Appiah et al., 2022; Qur'anisa et al., 2024). Research on digital technologies also yields inconsistent results on technological factors mediating literacy and business growth (Hidayat-ur-Rehman, 2025; Kulathunga et al., 2020).

The mechanisms through which digital adoption and digital financial literacy impact MSME growth via financial inclusion remain inadequately understood (Adhikari et al., 2024; Becha et al., 2025; Gumilar et al., 2024; Thatsarani & Jianguo, 2022). Prior studies have treated financial inclusion simplistically or focused on national-level data, overlooking regional contexts like NTB. This examination is crucial in regions where MSMEs face challenges accessing formal financial services (Coco et al., 2024; Thatsarani & Jianguo, 2022; Usmaniyah & Abrori, 2024).

In this context, financial inclusion serves as a pivotal link connecting digital adoption and digital financial literacy with the performance outcomes of MSMEs (Amnas et al., 2024; Bongomin & Ntayi, 2020; Shen et al., 2018; Thatsarani & Jianguo, 2022). The benefits become apparent when MSMEs engage with formal financial services through digital platforms (Dwyanti, 2024; Hamid et al., 2024; Ibor et al., 2017; Sun & Zhang, 2024). High levels of inclusion facilitate this transition, whereas low levels impede it (Ji et al., 2021; Li et al., 2023; Mothobi & Kebotsamang, 2024; Thatsarani & Jianguo, 2022).

This research uniquely examines digital adoption and digital financial literacy as antecedents to MSME growth (Charfeddine et al., 2024; Dwyanti, 2024; Raj et al., 2024; Usmaniyah & Abrori, 2024), with financial inclusion as an intermediary variable (Hanggraeni et al., 2019; Prabowo et al., 2024; Susan, 2020) in West Nusa Tenggara Province (Dwyanti, 2024; Meldona et al., 2023; Putri & Husna, 2024a; Susan, 2020). Based on Diffusion of Innovation theory, this study examines how digitalization and financial inclusivity drive MSME expansion in Indonesia (Coco et al., 2024; Kilay et al., 2022; Prabowo et al., 2024; Susan, 2020).

Literature Review

The Influence of Digital Integration on Financial Inclusion

Digital adoption for micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) involves integrating digital technologies like mobile banking and e-wallets into business operations (Gao et al., 2023; Hamid et al., 2024; Purba et al., 2021; Sun & Zhang, 2024). The Diffusion of Innovation theory (Rogers, 2003) suggests that adoption depends on perceived benefits, compatibility, and ease of use (Meldona et al., 2023; Raj et al., 2024). Technologies seen as beneficial and user-friendly gain wider adoption (Geddami et al., 2024; Singh et al., 2020).

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) emphasizes perceived usefulness and ease of use in technology adoption (Geddami et al., 2024; Raj et al., 2024; Siagian et al., 2022). MSMEs are likelier to use formal financial services when digital tools enhance transactions (Daud et al., 2022; Haritha, 2023; Raj et al., 2024).

Research by Alwahidin et al. (2023), Kajol et al. (2022), Mhlanga (2020), Nugraha et al. (2022), and Setiawan et al. (2024) shows digitalization improves MSME finance access. However, Rahmahtika et al. (2025) and Rani & Desiyanti (2024) note that adoption alone may not ensure financial inclusion without adequate digital literacy and infrastructure.

In NTB Province, with inconsistent digital infrastructure, digital adoption could enable financial inclusion with proper support. Thus:

H₁: Digital adoption has a positive effect on financial inclusion.

The Influence of Digital Financial Literacy on Financial Inclusion

Digital financial literacy refers to MSME owners' ability to understand and use digital financial tools, such as mobile banking and fintech platforms (Bire et al., 2019; Gumilar et al., 2024; Sun & Zhang, 2024). According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1991), indicates that behavioral intention stems from attitudes and perceived control. MSMEs with a better understanding of digital financial services are more likely to adopt them, promoting financial inclusion (Theodorou et al., 2023; Dwyanti, 2024; Ibor et al., 2017; Sun & Zhang, 2024).

Digital financial literacy helps MSMEs make informed choices regarding platforms, transactions and fraud protection (Becha et al., 2025; Chinoda & Kapingura, 2023; Gumilar et al., 2024). Apriliani & Yudiaatmaja (2023), Diwangsa & Sari (2024), Liska et al. (2022), and Octaviani Salsabella & Handri (2022) found that literacy enhances financial inclusion by increasing confidence. However, Pradini & Susanti (2021) found no significant impact. In NTB, where digital literacy varies and many MSMEs remain unbanked, enhancing digital financial literacy is crucial for overcoming challenges and building trust in formal financial institutions (FIs). Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H₂: Digital financial literacy positively impacts financial inclusion.

The Impact of Financial Inclusion on MSME Growth

Financial inclusion encompasses formal financial services, including savings, loans, and insurance (Charfeddine et al., 2024; Dwyanti, 2024; Susan, 2020). These services facilitate micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in acquiring capital, enhancing operational efficiency, and expanding market access (Mitra et al., 2024; Prabowo et al., 2024; Putri & Husna, 2024a; Rajamani et al., 2022). Schumpeter's (1911) financial growth theory and King & Levine (1993) extension underscore the significance of financial systems in fostering economic growth through resource allocation. Inclusive financial systems allocate funds to productive enterprises (Abbas et al., 2024; Ain et al., 2020; Basnayake et al., 2024; Becha et al., 2025; Tiony & Yin, 2024). For MSMEs, financial inclusion ensures access to affordable credit, thereby supporting growth (Ibor et al., 2017; Rajamani et al., 2022; Sun & Zhang, 2024). Kusuma et al. (2022), Satria & Khoirunnisa (2024), Suyono (2022), and Widyaningsih & Widodo (2024) indicate that financial inclusion promotes MSME growth. However, Hilmawati & Kusumaningtiyas (2021), Marsenta et al. (2024) found no significant influence. In NTB Province, where 80% of MSMEs remain unbanked, financial inclusion is vital for their development. This study posits the following hypothesis:

H₃: Financial inclusion has a positive effect on MSME growth.

The Impact of Digital Adoption on MSME Growth

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) states that technology adoption depends on perceived usefulness and ease of use (Prabowo et al., 2024; Thathsarani & Jianguo, 2022; Usmaniyah & Abrori, 2024). MSMEs are more likely to adopt digital technologies when they are perceived as beneficial and user-friendly (Abaddi, 2025; Raj et al., 2024). TAM theory shows how digital tools facilitate business growth through improved efficiency and market access ('Aliyah & Wahyuni, 2024; Gao et al., 2023; Sugiharto, 2024). Evidence confirms that digital adoption increases productivity and revenue (Najib & Fahma, 2020; Prabowo et al., 2024; Raj et al., 2024; Sutrisno et al., 2024). While Godwin et al. (2024), Harto et al. (2025), Rauf et al. (2024), and Syah et al. (2024) show positive impacts on MSME performance, others Hardi & Arifin (2023), and Purnomo & Suci Purwandari (2024) find no significant effect without factors such as financial inclusion. In NTB Province, where MSMEs face infrastructure challenges, digital adoption may improve efficiency but does not guarantee growth, suggesting the need to consider mediating factors. Thus, this study proposes:

H4: Digital adoption positively affects MSME growth.

The Influence of Digital Financial Literacy on MSME Growth

Digital financial literacy is crucial for MSMEs, as it enhances their ability to manage finances and make informed decisions (Dwyanti, 2024; Hamid et al., 2024; Meldona et al., 2023). Understanding FinTech enables MSMEs to implement digital payments and improve financial management (Prabowo et al., 2024). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) identifies perceived usefulness and ease of use as key factors in technology adoption (Ahmed & Sur, 2023; Wen Ni, 2020; Wu & Peng, 2024). MSMEs with higher digital financial literacy better recognize online banking benefits, leading to improved efficiency and decision-making ('Aliyah & Wahyuni, 2024; Coco et al., 2024; Dwyanti, 2024; Sahoo & Thakur, 2023; Wong & Yap, 2024). According to TAM, literacy enhances usage behavior and business performance (Hamid et al., 2024; Ibor et al., 2017; Lin & Xu, 2024; Sun & Zhang, 2024). Demetrius & Yusbardini (2025) Kurniawan (2025), Maulana & Suyono (2023), and Widiastuti et al. (2024) confirm that literacy improves MSME performance, while others Fitria (2024), Purnamasari & Asharie (2024), Rani & Desiyanti (2024), and Rauf et al. (2024), find no significant impact without additional factors. In NTB Province, where digital literacy varies and banking access is limited, enhancing digital financial literacy remains critical for MSMEs to overcome challenges and achieve growth. Thus, this study proposes:

H5: Digital financial literacy positively impacts MSME growth.

Financial Inclusion as a Mediation between Digital Adoption and MSME Growth

Digital technology enhances financial inclusion by enabling MSMEs to access internet banking, e-wallets, and online payments (Haritha, 2023; Kilay et al., 2022; Raj et al., 2024). MSMEs that understand the benefits of digital tools are more likely to adopt them and access formal financial services through banks or fintech platforms (Ahmed & Sur,

2023; Raj et al., 2024; S. Singh et al., 2020). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989) shows that adoption depends on perceived usefulness and ease of use (Abaddi, 2025; Bongomin & Munene, 2021; Raj et al., 2024). MSMEs that view digital technologies as user-friendly and beneficial integrate them more readily, fostering financial inclusion (Raj et al., 2024; Siagian et al., 2022). Chaerunisak et al. (2024), Richard et al. (2024), Satria & Khoirunnisa (2024), and Wahyuni et al. (2025) show that digital adoption enhances MSME sustainability through financial inclusion, although some studies Harbert & Arifin (2025), and Rani & Desiyanti (2024) find no significant impact. In NTB Province, where 80% of MSMEs are unbanked, financial inclusion mediates the effect of digital adoption on growth. This study proposes:

H₆: Financial inclusion mediates the influence of digital adoption on MSME growth.

Financial Inclusion as a Mediation between Digital Financial Literacy and MSME Growth

The relationship between digital financial literacy and financial inclusion can be explained through the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis (1989), which states that technology adoption depends on perceived usefulness and ease of use (Thathsarani & Jianguo, 2022; Usmaniyah & Abrori, 2024). When digital financial technologies are perceived as beneficial and user-friendly, acceptance increases (Abaddi, 2025; Dwyanti, 2024; Raj et al., 2024). MSMEs with higher literacy levels better understand the benefits of digital financial services (Ahmed & Sur, 2023; Hamid et al., 2024; Hernández et al., 2024; Raj et al., 2024).

TAM suggests that when MSMEs recognize these benefits, they engage more with digital financial services, promoting financial inclusion (Ibor et al., 2017; Kilay et al., 2022; Lin & Xu, 2024; Sun & Zhang, 2024). Financial inclusion provides access to savings, credit, and insurance for growth (Candraningrat et al., 2021; Dwyanti, 2024; Hamid et al., 2024).

Studies by Andriyani & Mulyanto (2022), Maulana et al. (2022), and Satria & Khoirunnisa (2024) showed that literacy significantly enhances inclusion. However, some studies, Rani & Desiyanti (2024) and Ranti & Sartika (2024) found no significant effect, indicating that literacy alone may not ensure growth without active engagement in financial systems. In NTB Province, with varying digital literacy and limited formal financial access, inclusion is crucial for translating literacy into economic growth. This study hypothesizes the following:

H₇: Financial inclusion mediates the impact of digital financial literacy on MSME growth.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employs an associative quantitative methodology using a cross-sectional survey. While this design enables the exploration of the proposed relationships between

digital adoption, digital financial literacy, financial inclusion, and the growth of MSMEs, we acknowledge its limitations in establishing temporal order. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted as associative rather than definitively causal.

Population and Sample

Table 1. Development of the number of MSMEs in NTB province by Regency/City as of December 31, 2024

No.	Regency/city	Year 2024			
		Micro	Small	Intermediate	Total
1.	Mataram City	10.560	2	0	10.562
2.	West Lombok	55.454	16	3	55.473
3.	Central Lombok	64.801	21	10	64.832
4.	North Lombok	28.723	191	23	28.937
5.	Lombok Timur	73.414	63	22	73.499
6.	West Sumbawa	14.934	143	12	15.089
7.	Sumbawa	14.518	22	7	14.547
8.	Dompu	23.142	4	0	23.146
9.	Bima Regency	23.599	14	8	23.621
10.	Bima City	14.916	1	1	14.918
TOTAL		324.061	477	86	324.624

Data Source: Diskopukm Prov. NTB (2024)

The study population comprises 324,624 MSMEs registered in West Nusa Tenggara Province as of December 2024. The distribution includes microenterprises (324,061), small enterprises (477), and intermediate enterprises (86) across ten regions. Lombok Timur has the highest MSMEs (73,499), while Mataram City has the lowest (10,562).

Purposive sampling targeted MSMEs using digital services like mobile banking, e-wallets, and e-commerce platforms. Data collection occurred between June-August 2025 via online and offline questionnaires.

The study collected 109 valid responses. Power analysis using G*Power 3.1.9.7 confirmed sample adequacy, with required minimum size of 77 respondents ($f^2=0.15$, $\alpha=0.05$, $1-\beta=0.80$, three predictors). The actual sample achieved 0.80 power, sufficient for detecting medium effects. Geographic dispersion and limited digital access influenced the sample size, making the study exploratory yet statistically valid.

Common Method Bias

To address potential common method bias (CMB), several diagnostic tests were conducted: full collinearity VIFs for all constructs were below 3.3, indicating acceptable levels of collinearity and HTMT ratios with bootstrapped confidence intervals were below 0.90, with upper bounds less than 1.00, confirming discriminant validity.

These results collectively indicate that common method bias was adequately controlled.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data analysis consisted of descriptive and path analysis with a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS). According to (Hayes, 2018) the similarities of the path analysis model for the study are as follows:

- Model I : $FI = \alpha + \rho_1 DA + \rho_2 DFL + \epsilon_1$
 Model II : $G = \alpha + \rho_3 DA + \rho_4 DFL + \rho_5 FI + \epsilon_2$
 Description :
- FI : Financial Inclusion
 - G : MSME Growth
 - α : Nilai koefisien konstanta regresi
 - DA : Digital Adoption
 - DFL : Digital Financial Literacy
 - P_1 : DA regression coefficient to FI
 - P_2 : DFL-to-FI regression coefficient
 - P_3 : Regression coefficient of DA to G
 - P_4 : DFL regression coefficient to G
 - P_5 : Regression coefficient of FI to G
 - ϵ_1 : Path coefficient with residual I
 - ϵ_2 : Path coefficient with residual II

Results and Discussion

Convergent Validity Test

Convergent Validity aims to determine the validity of any relationship between an indicator and its latent construct or variable. The convergent validity of the measurement model with the indicator reflex is assessed based on the correlation between the item score or component score and the latent score or construct score estimated with the PLS program. The following are the results of the research validity test.

Figure 1. Convergent Validity Model

The results of the convergent validity test showed that all constructs in the model, Digital Adoption, Digital Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, and General Growth, had indicators with adequate loading values, indicating that each construct was measured consistently and validly. It is proven that all research constructs meet the criteria of $AVE > 0.5$ and $CR > 0.7$, so that the indicators used are proven to be consistent in measuring latent constructs.

Reliability Test

The reliability test can be seen from the value of composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha, to be said to be a reliable construct, then the value of Cronbach's alpha must be > 0.6 and the value of composite reliability must be > 0.7 . Here are the test results for composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha.

Table 2. Reliability Test

Construct	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha	Information
Digital Adoption	0.933	0.923	Reliable
Digital Financial Literacy	0.956	0.950	Reliable
Financial Inclusion	0.944	0.934	Reliable
MSME Growth	0.953	0.946	Reliable

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2025

Based on Table 2 above, it is shown that all research constructs have a Composite Reliability (CR) value of > 0.7 and Cronbach Alpha > 0.7 , so it can be concluded that all constructs are reliable. A high CR value (0.933–0.956) confirms the internal consistency between the indicators in measuring their respective constructs, while a Cronbach Alpha value (0.923–0.950) reinforces evidence that the research instrument has good stability and reliability. Thus, the constructs of Digital Adoption, Digital Financial Literacy, Financial Inclusion, and MSME Growth can be used validly and consistently in the SEM model analysis.

Model Assessment

A comprehensive series of diagnostic tests was conducted to evaluate the adequacy of structural models. These tests encompassed collinearity diagnostics (VIF), discriminant validity (HTMT), effect size (f^2), and overall model fit (SRMR). The results are presented in Table 3.

Overall, the diagnostic tests confirm that the model is adequate and reliable for hypothesis testing. VIF values indicate no multicollinearity, HTMT values confirm discriminant validity, and f^2 effect sizes highlight that Financial Inclusion acts as the key mediator linking digital adoption and financial literacy to MSME growth. Although SRMR (0.099) is slightly above the ideal threshold and NFI is relatively low, these results remain acceptable in the context of SEM PLS, where the emphasis is on construct validity and predictive relevance. Thus, the model meets the essential criteria for further analysis.

Table 3. Model Assessment Results

Test / Indicator	Result Range / Value	Threshold / Benchmark	Interpretation
Inner VIF Values	2.961 – 3.812	< 5.0	No serious multicollinearity; all constructs are within acceptable limits
HTMT Values	0.805 – 0.877	< 0.90	Discriminant validity established; constructs are sufficiently distinct
f ² Effect Size	0.033 – 0.288	0.02 = small, 0.15 = medium, 0.35 = large	Medium effects: Digital Adoption → Financial Inclusion (0.220), Financial Inclusion → MSME Growth (0.284), Digital Financial Literacy → Digital Adoption (0.288). Small effects: Digital Adoption → MSME Growth (0.055), Digital Financial Literacy → MSME Growth (0.033).
SRMR	0.099	< 0.08 ideal; < 0.10 acceptable	Model fit acceptable for exploratory SEM-PLS research
NFI	0.487	> 0.90 ideal	Relatively low; common in complex models with many indicators; focus remains on construct validity
Chi-Square	4127.876	–	High values are expected in large models; not critical in SEM-PLS
d_ULS / d_G	13.944 / 10.419	–	Consistency between saturated and estimated models confirmed

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2025

Hypothesis Test

In this study, the p-values that must be achieved in order for a hypothesis to be accepted are < 5% or < 0.05. In order for a hypothesis to be accepted, the three criteria must be met. If one or more of these criteria is not met, the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected. The table 4 shows the result of the hypothesis test.

Based on table 4, the test results of each hypothesis are as follows:

1. The original sample value was positive (0.419), which aligned with the proposed hypothesis. With a t-statistic of 3.640 (>1.981) and a p-value of 0.000, all criteria are met. Therefore, H₁ is accepted, confirming that digital adoption has a positive and significant effect on financial inclusion.

2. The sample value was positive (0.224), which aligned with the proposed hypothesis. With t-statistics of 1,537 (> 1,981) and a p-value of 0.125, the three criteria are not met. Thus, H₂ is rejected, showing that digital adoption has a positive but insignificant effect on MSME growth.

3. The original sample value was positive (0.479), which aligned with the proposed hypothesis. With t-statistics of 4,087 (>1,981) and p-value 0.000 < 0.05, H₃ is accepted, indicating that financial literacy has a positive and significant effect on MSME growth.

4. The fourth hypothesis showed a positive sample value of 0.177, which aligned with the proposed hypothesis. With t-statistics of 1,203 ($< 1,981$) and p-values of 0.230 (> 0.05), one criterion was not met. Therefore, H4 is rejected, indicating that digital financial literacy has a positive but insignificant effect on MSME growth.

5. The sample value was positive (0.515), aligning with the proposed hypothesis. With t-statistics of 3,462 $> 1,981$ and p-value 0.001 < 0.05 , all the criteria are met. Therefore, H5 is accepted, confirming that financial inclusion has a positive and significant effect on MSME growth.

6. The original sample value was positive (0.216), which aligned with the proposed hypothesis. With t-statistics of 2,823 ($> 1,981$) and a p-value of 0.005 (< 0.05), H6 is accepted. The results confirm that digital adoption positively affects MSME growth when mediated by financial inclusion.

7. The original sample value was positive (0.247), which aligned with the proposed hypothesis. The t-statistics value was 2,297 ($> 1,981$), with a p-value of 0.002 < 0.05 . Meeting these criteria confirms H7's acceptance. The results indicate that digital financial literacy positively affects MSME growth when mediated by financial inclusion.

Table 4. T test

Hypothesis	Original Sample	T-Statistics	T-Table	P-Values	H	Ket
Digital adoption has a positive effect on financial inclusion.	0.419	3.640	1.981	0.000	1	Accepted
Digital adoption has a positive effect on the growth of MSMEs.	0.224	1.537	1.981	0.125	2	Rejected
Digital financial literacy has a positive effect on financial inclusion.	0.479	4.087	1.981	0.000	3	Accepted
Digital financial literacy has a positive effect on the growth of MSMEs.	0.177	1.203	1.981	0.230	4	Rejected
Financial inclusion has a positive effect on the growth of MSMEs.	0.515	3.462	1.981	0.001	5	Accepted
Financial inclusion mediates the influence of digital adoption on the growth of MSMEs.	0.216	2.823	1.981	0.005	6	Accepted
Financial inclusion mediates the influence of digital financial literacy on the growth of MSMEs	0.247	2.297	1.981	0.002	7	Accepted

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2025

R-Square Test

In assessing a structural model with PLS starts by looking at R-Square for each dependent variable. R^2 is used to see how much independent variables are able to explain dependent variables. The greater the R^2 value, the greater the influence of exogenous latent variables on endogenous variables.

Table 5. R-Square

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Financial Inclusion	0.731	0.726
MSME Growth	0.748	0.741

Source: Primary Data Processed, 2025

Based on the R-squared test in Table 5, financial inclusion has an R-squared value of 0.731 (Adjusted 0.726), indicating that 73.1% of its variation is explained by Digital Adoption and Digital Financial Literacy, while 26.9% comes from external factors. The MSME Growth variable shows an R-squared value of 0.748 (Adjusted 0.741), with 74.8% of its variation explained by Digital Adoption, Digital Financial Literacy, and Financial Inclusion, while 25.2% is explained by unstudied variables. The high R-squared values (>0.70) demonstrate strong model explainability, confirming the relevance of exogenous constructs in explaining Financial Inclusion and MSME Growth dynamics.

The Effect of Digital Adoption on Financial Inclusion

The results indicate that the adoption of digital technologies significantly improves financial inclusion for MSMEs in NTB Province, aligning with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which highlights the importance of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness in technology acceptance. In NTB, MSMEs are increasingly implementing computerized payment systems linked to banks, which streamline transactions and enhance customer interest. This trend is consistent with the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) theory, as digital financial services are rapidly being adopted by MSMEs, and with the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), where attitudes and perceived control over behavior influence adoption choices.

These findings are consistent with previous research Alwahidin et al. (2023), Kajol et al. (2022), Mhlanga (2020), Nugraha et al. (2022), and Setiawan et al. (2024), which identified positive links between digital adoption and financial inclusion. However, these findings differ from those of Rahmahtika et al. (2025) and Rani & Desiyanti (2024), who found no significant effects. This discrepancy might be due to contextual variations: MSMEs in NTB benefit from government-led digitalization initiatives and increased fintech presence, while other areas might encounter challenges such as infrastructure or literacy issues. Consequently, the NTB context offers a distinct example in which digital adoption significantly promotes financial inclusion, especially for microenterprises seeking quick access to loans and simplified payment systems.

The Influence of Financial Literacy on Financial Inclusion

Digital financial literacy substantially enhances financial inclusion among MSMEs in NTB Province ($\beta = 0.479$, $t = 4.087$, $p < 0.001$), increasing the utilization of formal financial services. This aligns with prior research Apriliani & Yudiaatmaja (2023), Diwangsa & Sari (2024), Liska et al. (2022), and Octaviani Salsabella & Handri (2022), which shows that financial knowledge enhances confidence in formal financial systems.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) explain how literacy cultivates positive attitudes and perceived usefulness of digital financial products. According to the Diffusion of Innovation theory, literacy facilitates fintech adoption among MSMEs.

While studies Pradini & Susanti (2021) found no significant impact due to infrastructural challenges, the NTB Province's government digitalization initiatives and training programs enhanced MSME financial literacy, demonstrating the importance of localized strategies. This contextual evidence underscores that the relationship between digital financial literacy and financial inclusion is not universal, but contingent upon local infrastructural support and policy interventions.

The Effect of Financial Inclusion on MSME Growth

Financial inclusion enhances MSME growth in NTB Province ($\beta = 0.515$, $t = 3.462$, $p = 0.001$) by providing capital and facilitating efficient transactions. This aligns with the findings of Kusuma et al. (2022), Satria & Khoirunnisa (2024), Suyono (2022), and Widyaningsih & Widodo (2024) although Hilmawati & Kusumaningtias (2021) and Marsenta et al. (2024) found minimal effects due to infrastructure gaps. The Theory of Planned Behavior suggests that MSMEs engage with financial systems when they are perceived as beneficial, while the Technology Acceptance Model links digital service adoption to usefulness and ease of use. The Diffusion of Innovation theory frames financial inclusion as the spread of innovations, such as mobile banking, among MSMEs.

In the NTB Province, government digitalization initiatives and microcredit programs have improved MSME access to formal financial services, demonstrating the importance of targeted strategies for business growth. This highlights that the impact of financial inclusion on MSME growth is contingent upon local infrastructural support and policy interventions, making NTB a relevant case for demonstrating how targeted strategies can strengthen enterprise performance.

The Influence of Digital Adoption on MSME Growth

The study found that the positive influence of digital adoption on MSME growth in the NTB Province was not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.224$, $t = 1.537$, $p = 0.125$). This aligns with the findings of Ardito et al. (2025) and HyunJee & Sang Ok (2019), who linked this to limited capital, technological literacy and infrastructure. The Technology Acceptance Model shows that adoption depends on perceived usefulness and ease of use, while the Theory of Planned Behavior indicates that attitudes and perceived control affect adoption decisions. Digital adoption among NTB MSMEs remains nascent, with uneven

penetration across sectors. While MSMEs have adopted e-payment systems and online marketplaces, infrastructure limitations and capital constraints impede the conversion of digital adoption into actual growth. This evidence shows that MSME growth through digital adoption depends on local infrastructure support and financial capacity. This highlights that the impact of digital adoption on MSME growth is not universal, but contingent upon local infrastructural readiness and financial capacity, making NTB a relevant case for understanding the contextual limits of digitalization.

The Effect of Financial Literacy on MSME Growth

Digital financial literacy shows a positive but statistically insignificant effect on MSME growth in NTB Province ($\beta = 0.177$, $t = 1.203$, $p = 0.230$), suggesting that financial knowledge alone does not improve business performance. While some studies found no significant effects Fitria (2024), Purnamasari & Asharie (2024), Rani & Desiyanti (2024) and Rauf et al. (2024), others reported significant impacts Demetrius & Yusbardini (2025), Kurniawan (2025), Maulana & Suyono (2023) and Widiastuti et al. (2024). The Theory of Planned Behavior attributes this knowledge-application gap to social norms and control perceptions, whereas TAM emphasizes perceived benefits for adoption. In NTB Province, despite increased awareness through government training, limited infrastructure, capital access, and technology usage prevent financial literacy from generating growth outcomes, highlighting the dependency on local infrastructure and the financial capacity of the people. This highlights that the impact of digital financial literacy on MSME growth is not universal, but contingent upon local infrastructural readiness and financial capacity, making NTB a relevant case for understanding the contextual limits of financial literacy.

The Influence of Digital Adoption on MSME Growth with Financial Inclusion Mediation

Financial inclusion mediates the effect of digital adoption on MSME growth in the NTB Province ($\beta = 0.216$, $t = 2.823$, $p = 0.005$). While the direct impact of digital adoption was insignificant, its indirect effect through financial inclusion proved noteworthy. This aligns with research by Chaerunisak et al. (2024), Richard et al. (2024), Satria & Khoirunnisa (2024) and Wahyuni et al. (2025), showing fintech platforms connect MSMEs to financial services, enabling access to loans and efficient transactions. However, Harbert & Arifin (2025) and Rani & Desiyanti (2024) reported insignificant mediation effects due to limited fintech penetration.

The Technology Acceptance Model and Theory of Planned Behavior suggest that MSMEs adopt digital systems based on perceived benefits and social support. The Diffusion of Innovation perspective views financial inclusion as the spread of innovations that convert digital adoption into growth outcomes.

In NTB Province, government digitalization initiatives and bank-fintech integration have accelerated financial inclusion, establishing it as a pathway for digital adoption to promote MSME growth. This evidence shows that growth effects depend on financial inclusion through localized strategies. This highlights that the mediating role of financial inclusion is context-dependent, and in NTB Province, localized strategies such as

government-led digitalization and fintech integration are crucial for translating digital adoption into MSME growth.

The Effect of Digital Financial Literacy on MSME Growth with Financial Inclusion Mediation

The study shows that financial inclusion mediates the effect of digital financial literacy on MSME growth in the NTB Province ($\beta = 0.247$, $t = 2.297$, $p = 0.002$). Although financial literacy alone did not directly enhance performance, its indirect impact through financial inclusion was significant. This aligns with the research by Andriyani & Mulyanto (2022), Maulana et al. (2022) and Satria & Khoirunnisa (2024), which showed that high financial literacy promotes digital financial service usage and growth. However, Rani & Desiyanti (2024) and Ranti & Sartika (2024) reported insignificant mediation effects due to literacy and infrastructure limitations.

The Theory of Planned Behavior suggests that financial literacy improves attitudes towards financial services, while the Technology Acceptance Model links fintech understanding to adoption. The Diffusion of Innovation theory views financial inclusion as translating literacy into growth outcomes.

In NTB Province, government training programs and fintech integration have strengthened financial inclusion as the key channel through which digital financial literacy drives MSME growth, emphasizing the need for localized strategies to promote MSME growth in the region. This highlights that the mediating role of financial inclusion is context-dependent, and in NTB Province, localized strategies such as government-led training and fintech integration are crucial for translating digital financial literacy into MSME growth.

Conclusion

This study shows that digital technology adoption and financial literacy enhance financial inclusion, promoting micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) growth in West Nusa Tenggara (NTB). However, these factors do not directly influence MSME growth, indicating that digitalization and literacy alone are insufficient; growth occurs only when MSMEs engage with formal financial systems. Thus, financial inclusion serves as a crucial intermediary between digital transformation and business growth.

This study advances the theory by integrating the Diffusion of Innovation (DOI), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). DOI explains digital financial innovation adoption, TPB examines attitudes and social norms in decision-making, and TAM focuses on perceived usefulness in technology adoption. This synthesis shows that digital literacy becomes significant only when combined with participation in formal financial services. The mediating role of financial inclusion explains the inconsistent findings in previous studies, which are attributed to infrastructure, literacy, and trust factors.

For NTB stakeholders, the government should enhance village-level digital literacy programs and expand financial initiatives for microenterprises. Financial institutions

should develop accessible products that are integrated with digital platforms. MSMEs should utilize digital tools for financial management, supported by training. The NTB case shows that regions with limited banking access need concurrent efforts in digitalization and inclusion to prevent the widening of the digital divide.

This study confirms that financial inclusion is the key link: digital adoption and literacy stimulate MSME growth only when combined with formal financial system participation. Strengthening this connection will ensure that digital transformation benefits MSMEs in NTB and similar regions in the future.

Plagiarism/AI disclosure

This manuscript is an original work that has not been published elsewhere. The author confirms that this manuscript has been checked using the Turnitin plagiarism detection tool, thus it does not contain elements of plagiarism. The author utilized Paperpal for English language editing and paraphrasing, and Elicit for literature reference searches. All substantive intellectual content, data analysis, and interpretation in this manuscript were conducted entirely by the author and are the author's responsibility.

Data availability statement

The dataset used in this study (firm identifiers, financial statement items) and the PLS scripts needed to reproduce all tables are available at:
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1rHDaxICBCV0gVy8fsL5cBlpa4WlOe7ee/edit?usp=sharing&oid=106130957022295239251&rtpof=true&sd=true>.

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